

Stress Management Intervention Plan for DepEd Youth Formation Coordinators

Rationale

The Philippine Constitution guarantees the right of workers to humane working conditions, a just wage, and security of tenure. Also, the Civil Service Commission (CSC) has issued guidelines and policies on the promotion of health and wellness in the workplace. As a government agency, the Department of Education (DepEd) is bound by the provisions of the Constitution and policies issued by the CSC, especially in ensuring that its employees are provided with a safe and healthy working environment, including the promotion of health and wellness in the workplace.

The YFD is responsible for designing and implementing programs that promote the holistic development of students, with the aim of preparing them to become responsible and productive members of society. This office is also tasked with ensuring the well-being of its Youth Formation Coordinators (YFCs) and providing them with a healthy working environment.

According to the DepEd Order No. 12, s. 2019, or the "Guidelines on the Implementation of Mental Health and Psychosocial Support Services for DepEd Personnel," mandates the establishment of mental health and psychosocial support services in DepEd offices and schools. These services include stress management programs, counseling services, and other activities to promote the mental health and well-being of DepEd personnel, including the YFCs. It also includes the initiatives to support the physical health and well-being of non-teaching personnel, such as promoting physical activity and healthy lifestyles, providing access to medical and dental services, and implementing workplace safety and health programs.

After analyzing and interpreting the result of this study, it was found that even though the stress level of DepEd Youth Formation Coordinators was moderate level, there were still items with a high result that need immediate attention to ensure that they are mentally and physically healthy while performing their tasks.

Objectives

This research paper aimed to formulate an intervention plan for the DepEd Youth Formation Coordinators to help them minimize or eradicate the stress they are experiencing within the organization while performing their job and ensure the efficient and effective delivery of learner formation initiatives in schools within their jurisdiction within the four (4) areas: nature of work, work relationship, organizational role, and career development.

This research shows that Youth Formation Coordinators (YFCs) moderately experience stress within their office. Due to this finding, a stress management intervention plan shall reduce the negative effects of stress on YFCs, improve their overall health and well-being, boost their productivity and performance, and foster a positive work culture within the workplace.

PROPOSED STRESS MANAGEMENT INTERVENTION PLAN FOR DEPED YOUTH FORMATION COORDINATORS

Areas of Concern	Findings	Objectives	Activities	Time Frame	Budget (P)	Persons Involved	Success Indicator
Nature of Work	The study has found that item number 2. "I perform heavy or excessive workloads in a day or week" got the highest mean.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ensure that Youth Formation Coordinators understand their roles and responsibilities clearly. 2. Provide a platform for open communication and feedback. 	<p>Virtual nationwide assembly:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Orientation of new Youth Formation Coordinators (YFC) and re-orientation of existing YFC in relation to their job descriptions and Key Result Areas (KRA). 2. Interface activity/ Feedbacking session. 3. Maintain a social media platform for constant communication with field counterparts 	Every Year	No budget is needed since it is purely virtual.	10 – YFD CO Staff 450 – Regional and Division YFC Total: 460	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Oriented and Re-oriented YFC 2. Issued policies addressing challenges of YFC 3. Established communication platform
Work relationship	The results revealed that item number 1 and 8, "There is a lack of support or help from my coworkers,	Provide program support funds to support the implementation of learner formation.	Downloading of Program Support Funds to support learner formation initiatives.	Every Year	Downloading of Program Support Funds = 8,000,000.00	5 – YFD CO Staff	Activities initiated by Division and Regional Offices

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	especially accomplishing a task." and "I receive the limited provision of resources for my position like work-related gadgets," registered the highest mean.						
Organizational Role	The data gathered revealed that item number 4, "I have too much responsibility," obtained the highest mean.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Clarify the roles and responsibilities of the coordinators and provide clear expectations for their performance. 2. Assess and review the current organizational structure in Regional and Division Offices. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Assessment Survey on the Current Situation of YFCs through Microsoft Form. 2. Organization Structure Review and Assessment Workshop 	FY 2023	Organization Structure Review and Assessment Workshop Board and Lodging = 350,000.00 Materials = 10,500.00 Traveling Expense = 75,000.00 Total: 435,500.00	3-BHROD Staff 7-YFD CO Staff 5 -Operation Strand ExeCom Staff 20-YFCs (RO/SDO) Total: 35	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Updated Job Description for PDO I/YFC 2. Career Pathing Plan for PDO I/ YFC 3. Rationalization Plan
Career Development	The study exposed that item number 2, "there was a lack of opportunity	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Provide training and development opportunities for the coordinators to improve their skills and 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop and conduct a training need assessment 2. Create a training 	FY 2023	<i>Development of training matrix</i>	<i>Development of training matrix</i> 3-BHROD Staff	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. YFC completed the capacity-building program 2. Sustainable and accessible

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	for advancement within the organization," gained the highest mean.	<p>knowledge related to their roles.</p> <p>2. Foster a supportive work environment by promoting open communication, recognizing and rewarding positive behaviors and accomplishments , and promoting a culture of respect and support.</p> <p>3. Provide coordinators with the necessary resources and support to perform their roles effectively, such as access to training.</p>	<p>matrix or learning and development framework</p> <p>3. Conduct a series of training (face-to-face)</p> <p>4. Develop and disseminate self-paced training through the National Education Portal.</p>		<p>Board and Lodging = 350,000.00</p> <p>Materials = 9,100.00</p> <p>Traveling Expense =20,000.00</p> <p>Total: 379,100.00</p> <p><i>Learner Formators Capacity Building Program (In-person)</i></p> <p>Board and Lodging = 4,400,000</p> <p>Supplies and Materials = 75,000.00</p> <p>Traveling Expense (CO Staff) = 120,000.00</p> <p>Honorarium for Speakers = 60,000</p> <p>Total: 4,655,000.00</p>	<p>7-YFD CO Staff</p> <p>5 -Operation Strand ExeCom Staff</p> <p>20-YFCs (RO/SDO)</p> <p>Total: 35</p> <p><i>Learner Formators In-Person Capacity Building Program</i></p> <p>10 - YFD CO Staff</p> <p>450 - Regional and Division YFC</p> <p>Total: 460</p> <p><i>Learner Formators</i></p>	<p>platform for learner formators capacity building</p>

Areas of Concern	Findings	Objectives	Activities	Time Frame	Budget (P)	Persons Involved	Success Indicator
					<p><i>Learner Formators Capacity Building Program (Self-paced/Virtual)</i></p> <p>Honorarium for Speakers = 200,000 Filipino Sign Language Interpreter = 50,000.00</p> <p>Total: 150,000.00</p> <p>Grand Total: 5,184,100.00</p>	<p><i>Capacity Building Program (Self-paced/Virtual)</i></p> <p>5 - YFD CO Staff 2 - NEAP CO Staff 3 - BHROD CO Staff 450 - Regional and Division YFC</p> <p>Total: 460</p>	